

PRESCHOOL EDUCATION SYSTEM IN OUR COUNTRY AND IN FOREIGN COUNTRIES

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Annotation: In this article, the author talks about the importance of preschool education system in Uzbekistan and foreign countries, its form and essence.

Keywords: Preschool education, upbringing, system, comparative pedagogy, comparativism, unique Japanese method.

Аннотация: В данной статье автор рассказывает о значении системы дошкольного образования в Узбекистане и зарубежных странах, ее форме и сущности.

Ключевые слова: Дошкольное образование, воспитание, система, сравнительная педагогика, компаративизм, уникальный японский метод.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, great attention is paid to the field of preschool education today. The field of preschool education is considered the primary link in the continuous education system, which plays a very important role in raising a healthy and well-rounded child and preparing him for school. During the years of independence, the education system and the upbringing of a well-rounded generation in the republic have risen to the level of the main priority areas of state policy. It is no secret that the prestige and role of preschool educational organizations in our country are constantly growing.

Our state has set itself a number of tasks, such as introducing advanced pedagogical and information technologies into the preschool education process, ensuring the implementation of an information system for managing preschool education, as well as preparing and producing educational and methodological, didactic materials for preschool educational organizations. Scientific research is being conducted on the development of preschool education worldwide, creating the necessary conditions for their comprehensive intellectual, moral, aesthetic and physical development, taking into account advanced foreign experiences.

Indeed, in the past short period of time, the resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-98 dated July 2, 2024 “On measures to improve the state administration system in the field of preschool and school education”, No. 423 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 8, 2025 “On approval of the professional standard of a preschool educational organization

pedagogue”, No. 867 dated December 20, 2024 “On improving the system of continuous professional development of preschool and school education employees”, No. 848 dated December 18, 2024 “On additional measures to digitize the preschool education system and further improve the activities of preschool educational organizations” indicate that the reforms being implemented in the field of preschool education are entering a new stage.

Also, the improved state curriculum "First Step" serves to organize the activities of preparatory groups based on modern pedagogical approaches. This program widely uses game technologies, activity-based training, work in small groups and integrated training. Within the framework of the "Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy, projects are also being implemented to develop a digital educational environment in preschool educational organizations. In particular, groups equipped with interactive boards, tablets and multimedia resources are being organized in some state preschool educational organizations.

When studying the problem of introducing the experience of foreign countries into the educational process of Uzbekistan, it is necessary to know when the development of education among countries and its comparative analysis dates back. Therefore, in order to further develop preschool educational organizations in our country, we should also study other foreign preschool educational organizations.

The science of comparative pedagogy deals with the education system of countries, developed countries in general, their achievements, and their development, and there is also a history of the origin of this science. Comparative pedagogy was originally formed in the field of philosophical sciences and studied various issues, including the development of the problems of education of the younger generation in the countries of the world. Even in ancient times, in the context of philosophical teachings, there was a lot of information about how children were educated in different peoples and countries. They generalized educational methods and values, and analyzed the specific aspects of how life experience is transmitted from the older generation to the younger generation.

Each nation has its own national values, and the role of the younger generations in their growth from century to century is, of course, incomparable. In modern language, comparative pedagogy is also called comparativism. Comparatism (Latin comparativis - comparative) means comparison and comparison, and embodies the identification of similar and different aspects of historical development trends, the separation of mutually compatible aspects of similar phenomena. The introduction of foreign experience into the field of preschool education has been gaining serious momentum in recent years. In developed countries of the world, studying and implementing achievements in the field of preschool education is one of the main

issues required of educators. In particular, in Germany, attention is very high to child education. This can be seen from the establishment of the Ministry of "Family" in the country. Here, representatives of the "Jugendamt" get acquainted with the conditions of a family that has a child immediately after birth. If the parents are not financially able to raise a child or are morally and spiritually incapable, the child is taken away from them. In terms of upbringing, Germans try not to waste the child's time, to keep him busy, and not to waste his free time. In Germany, the authorities place children in preschool educational institutions. Information is collected about the ethnic origin of children and their religion, and great attention is paid to this in preschool educational institutions. Pork is not added to the food of children belonging to the Islamic religion, a separate dish is prepared for them.

In France, it has become customary to send children to kindergarten from infancy. Firstly, this gives women the opportunity to work, and secondly, they adapt to society from infancy and grow up to be independent. From a young age, a French child goes to school independently, buys things in a store, and is left alone at home. Although mothers scold their children with their voices, they never hit them. Society protects the rights of children through a number of laws. Parents and guardians are primarily responsible for the development and health of children.

In Italy, children do not go to kindergarten until they are three years old; in addition to their parents, their grandparents, aunts, uncles, and cousins are also involved in their upbringing. A child grows up in a large family. In Italy, they tolerate all the whims of children, constantly give them gifts, and almost never punish them. Sometimes an Italian mother yells at her child out of anger, but she immediately kisses, hugs, and comforts him. In Italy, a child attends kindergarten from the age of three. Here, they are taught to read and write, prepare for school, and learn to adapt to the team. Team games and performances are regularly staged, a foreign language is taught twice a week, and they acquire various skills and qualifications for going to school, learn to communicate with friends.

In Japan, preschool education institutions are much more developed than in other countries. In Japan, preschool education institutions solve the following tasks: helping a child to develop good relationships with adults and children, respect for nature, form a healthy lifestyle, and acquire social behavior skills. Preschool education in Japan is positively evaluated: it helps to raise a child who is not spoiled and able to work with other children. In addition, in Japan there are additional schools for gymnastics, music, dance, art, swimming, etc., as well as private kindergartens that prepare for entering the universities where they are located. In kindergarten in Japan, from 7:00 everyone plays freely with each other, at 9:30 the song "Put everything in its place" is played, after which the children practice 10

funny songs on the street. At the break, the song "Everyone in their groups" is played, and the children take off their shoes in the lobby and return to their groups. The children count and talk about the time of year. Then, under the guidance of the teacher, the children complete the task in the workbook for 30 minutes, counting and coloring. While completing the task, the children start playing games. After 20 minutes of such games, preparation for the meal begins. The children bring breakfast from home in a box, take cups and napkins. The kindergarten adds a hot plate and a bottle of milk to the items brought from home. Then the children sing a song together and start eating, each eating at their own pace: from 10 to 45 minutes. The educator sits with the children at different tables every day. After eating, each child removes the stick and box.

The most interesting thing is that the Japanese use the "unique Japanese method" for raising children, and this method is as follows: "Up to 5 years old, a child is a king, from 5 to 15 years old - a slave, and after 15 years old - an equal". Other nations interpret this statement differently. Of course, this philosophical phrase should not be taken literally. But, in fact, a child's life is divided into several periods, and the first is the period when the child is admired, loved and pampered. With age, in addition to pleasures, the child becomes responsible for his actions and a number of tasks, having reached a certain stage of growth and development, yesterday's child becomes a full-fledged and equal member of society. All this was harmoniously and consistently observed in the children's education system in Japan, and today this method has yielded the expected results.

Kindergartens in China are large, with an average of 270 children and a team of 60 educators. There are 26 children in a group, some of whom stay in kindergarten from 8:00 to 18:00 during the day and go home in the evening. Some (5%) stay overnight. They go home on Wednesdays and Saturdays. Admission to kindergarten begins at 7:45. As you know, China is a very populous country. Therefore, the Chinese state has a strict policy in the field of family planning. Each family should not have more than one child. The limitation of the number of children in a family is reflected in the attitude of parents towards their children. In a Chinese family, they pamper each and every child, trying to give them a good education. Strict order and discipline are established in kindergarten, and childishness is prohibited.

Modern life today is unimaginable without the development of science, enlightenment and education, as if humanity revolves around the axis of science. It is not for nothing that the development of education is defined as the first task in the leading countries of the world. After all, the future prosperity of our country is closely related to the achievements we have made in this area. Today, the educational activities of the continuing education sector are being further improved,

and the centuries-old aspiration of our people towards knowledge is once again being manifested. Our young people are striving to live a healthy and beautiful life, to get a permanent job in their chosen profession, to take responsibility, not to allow their human dignity to be degraded, in short, to achieve perfection, and in this process they see education as the most important condition.

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